

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF BUYING PRODUCTS THROUGH ONLINE

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Abstract:

Online shopping that glorious invention which allows people to buy things from the comfort of their homes. No more travelling to multiple stores to find the right product; no more having to deal with over-enthusiastic sales persons; no more standing in long lines at the checkout counter. The e-commerce boom has certainly changed the way we shop for the better. But, like everything else, the world of online shopping is not all roses. Despite all the efforts of e-commerce companies to alleviate them, there are a few problems that customers still have to face while shopping online.

Key Words: Online Shopping & Shopping

Introduction:

Online shopping that glorious invention which allows people to buy things from the comfort of their homes. No more travelling to multiple stores to find the right product; no more having to deal with over-enthusiastic sales persons; no more standing in long lines at the checkout counter. The e-commerce boom has certainly changed the way we shop for the better. But, like everything else, the world of online shopping is not all roses. Despite all the efforts of e-commerce companies to alleviate them, there are a few problems that customers still have to face while shopping online.

Objective of the Study:

- To study the factors reframing shopping on the internets and features necessary for an online shopping site
- Finding the problems and give suggestions

Scope of the Study:

From this study, It was found why customers hesitate to make decision for shopping online. I analyse the various problems faced by the customers on online shopping. Find the reasons and gave the suggestions for the problems faced by the customers. Also find out the ways to overcome the problems faced by customers. Found, what are the fraud activities done on online shopping.

Methodology:

Research Design:

Research Design Research design is the detailed plan of conducting a research study. Descriptive research design has been used in the study.

Descriptive Research Design:

Descriptive Research Design Descriptive analysis attempts to explain systematically a trend, and provides data concerning attitudes and preferences towards a problem.

Sample Area:

The data has been collected from POLLACHI the city is have urban and rural area. But my study was conducted by middle of the city

Sample Technique:

Sampling technique is the choice of a subset of people from among a huge population to estimate characteristics of the 80 respondents. The focused to collection people who going to work.

Limitations of the Study:

The study has got certain limitation of which a few are listed below:

- The study is confined to selected Pollachi city only.
- The study is based upon the consumer behaviours and problems of online shopping.
- The data collected for the research is fully on primary data given by the respondents.

Tools and Techniques Used:

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi-Square Test

Analysis of Data:

- Data so collected was tabulated suitably for the purpose of analysis
- Appropriate statistical tool like data analysis, tabulations, and other tools were used for analysis and interpretation of data

Source of Data Collection:

Data for this study was unique in several respects. The study was based on the primary and secondary data both of which were important for the analysis of consumer behaviour during online shopping. Data was collected through primary and secondary sources.

Primary Data:

Primary data is that information which is collected by researchers themselves during their own research. Primary data speaks for itself and readers automatically want to read the research matter. This information is specifically gathered for own research needs. Primary data are fresh, new and collected first time directly by the researcher himself for his research project.

Questionnaire Method:

Data was collected through questionnaire method. This method of data collection particularly it was being collected by working people, in this method questionnaires were collected answer met face to face.

Type of Sampling:

Random Sampling:

One of the best probability sampling techniques that helps in saving time and resources, is the simple random sampling method. It is a reliable method of obtaining information where every single member by chance. Each individual has the same probability of being chosen to be a part of a sample.

Analysis:

Gender:

Gender	Count	Percentage
Male	37	46.25%
Female	43	53.75%
Total	80	100%

Education:

Educational	Count	Percentage
UG Degree	52	65.00%
PG Degree	18	22.50%
Others	10	12.50%
Total	80	100%

Necessary of an Online Shopping Site:

	Percentage
Multiple Payment Gateways	31%
Social Networking Integration	2%
Privacy And Secure Checkout	17%
Design	23%
Customer Friendly	27%
Total	100%

The respondent 31% said necessary for an online shopping site is multiple payment gateways, next 27% customer friendly, 23% design, 17% privacy and secure checkout, 2% social networking integration with the statement of necessary for an online shopping site majority of respondents necessary for online site is multiple payment gateway.

Biggest Concern about Online Shopping:

	Percentage
Breach of Personal Information	3.75%
Breach of Payment Details	38.75%
Poor Internet Connection	2.50%
All of These Above	55%

The biggest concern about online shopping segment has been divided into 4 categories, breach of personal information, breach of personal details, poor internet connection and all these above majority of the 55% respondents choose the all the above 38.75% respondents breach of payment details, 3.75% respondents said breach of personal information, 2.50% respondents said poor internet connections, majority of the respondents 55% choose the all the above.

Important Factor In Reframing From Shopping On The Internet						
	1	2	3	4	5	Total
A) Waiting to Receive The Product	31	39	2	7	1	80
Percentage	38.75	48.75	2.5	8.75	1.25	
B) Risk of Credit Card Transaction	20	25	17	16	2	80
Percentage	25	31.25	21.25	20	2.5	

C) Difficulty in Returning Products	12	15	10	31	12	80
Percentage	15	18.75	12.5	38.75	15	
D) Risk of Not Getting What I Paid	15	18	18	19	10	80
Percentage	18.75	22.5	22.5	23.75	12.5	
E) Risk of Losing Privacy	8	2	8	50	12	80
Percentage	10	2.5	10	62.5	15	
F) Lack of Trust Worthiness of Vendors	2	4	2	39	33	80
Percentage	2.5	5	2.5	48.75	41.25	
G) Not Being Able to Touch Products	2	10	42	26	0	80
Percentage	2.5	12.5	52.5	32.5	0	
H) More Expensive than Sold in Retail Shop	15	18	0	38	9	80
Percentage	18.75	22.5	0	47.5	11.25	
I) Complex Compared to Traditional Shopping	22	39	2	14	3	80
Percentage	27.5	48.75	2.5	17.5	3.75	

A) Waiting to Receive the Product:

Out of 80 respondents 48% shopping one the internet waiting to receive the product method reframing is important. Majority respondents said quick to receive the product customer's needs. 38.75% respondents said very important reframing that factor, 25% indifferent, 8.75 unimportant, 1.25% very important.

B) Risk of Credit Card Transaction:

Out of 80 respondents 31.25% important factor reframing risk of credit card transaction 26.25% very important, 21.25% respondents said indifferent because they were not buy the product through online transaction. 20% respondents said no issue of their current transaction 2.5% very unimportant.

C) Difficulty in Returning Product:

38.75% respondents unimportant reframing factor of difficulty in returning products. According analysis they were not face returning issues. 15% very important, 18.75 % important, 12.5% indifferent, 15% very unimportant.

D) Risk of Not Getting What I Paid:

23.75% respondents unimportant reframing factor of risk of not getting what I paid. 22.5% important reframing, 22.5% important, 18.75% important, 11.25 % very unimportant, the study revealed negative and positive is equally

E) Risk of Losing Privacy:

62.5% respondents its unimportant factors of reframing. Because they were not facing any problems in losing privacy.10% very important, 2.5% important, 10% indifferent, very unimportant of this factors doing reframing.

F) Lack Trust Worthiness of Vendors:

48.75% respondents unimportant factors of reframing is lack of trust worthiness of vendors. Because no issues of vendors now a days. 2.5% very important, 5 % important, 2.5% indifferent, 40% very important.

G) Not Being Able to Touch Products:

52.5% respondents indifferent factors reframing not being able to touch products, 2.5% very important, 12.5% important, 32.5% unimportant, 0% very unimportant.

H) More Expensive Than Sold in Retail Shop:

47.5% unimportant factors reframing of more expensive than sold in retail shop. 18.75% very important, 22.5% important, 11.25% very unimportant majority of the respondents unimportant reframing factor of more expensive than sold in retail shop.

I) Complex Compared to Traditional Shopping:

48.75% respondents said important factor of reframing on the internet complex compared to traditional shopping, 27.5% very important, 25% indifferent, 17.5 % unimportant to reframing complex compared to traditional shopping

Chi- Square:

Monthly Income and Single Online Purchase:

Monthly Income	Less Than 1,000	1,000 To 5,000	Total
Single Online Purchase			
Less Than 20,000	12	0	12
21,000 To 30,000	33	1	34
31,000 To 40,000	12	9	21
41,000 To 50,000	8	1	9
More Than 50,000	4	0	4
Total	69	11	80

Corresponding row * corresponding column

Grand Total:

Monthly Income Single Online Purchase	Less Than 1,000	1,000 To 5,000
Less Than 20,000	12*69/80=10.35	12*11/80=1.65
21,000 To 30,000	34*69/80=29.32	34*11/80=4.56
31,000 To 40,000	21*69/80=18.11	21*11/80=2.88
41,000 To 50,000	9*69/80=7.76	9*11/80=1023
More Than 50,000	4*69/80=3.45	4*11/80=0.55

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Monthly Income Single Online Purchase	Less Than 1,000	1,000 To 5,000
Less Than 20,000	0.4	2
21,000 To 30,000	0.55	3.2
31,000 To 40,000	2	12
41,000 To 50,000	0	0
More Than 50,000	0.125	1

Calculated value = 21.275

Level of significant (0.05)

Degree of freedom =(r-1)*(c-1)

$$= (2-1)*(5-1) = 1*4 = 4$$

Table value = 11.07

TV ≥ CV = Ho accepted null hypothesis

TV ≤ CV = Ha alternative hypothesis

This study TV ≤ CV – Ha alternative hypothesis accepted.

Findings and Suggestion:

Out of 80 respondents majority of respondents felt in the problems while conducting online purchase, Kind of problems.

Quality Issues:

The biggest problem while buying things online is that you have no guarantee of a product's quality. Reviews are not always reliable and all the research can't assure you of a product's quality; fraudulent sellers who intentionally mislead customers to increase sales are the prime reason for faulty/sub-par products being sold online. With the volume of goods e-commerce companies handle these days, it can be quite difficult for them to conduct quality checks on each and every one of the products they're selling. Additionally, the issue of getting the correct size remains a serious drawback for buying clothing and footwear online. Sizes vary from brand to brand, and since you can't try out the products before buying them, selecting the size is always a gamble.

Digital Payment Failures:

Whether a customer is paying by credit/debit card, net banking, or one of the several digital wallets that exist today, the failure of digital payments always looms overhead while making online transactions. A faltering internet connection or a technical glitch often results in the payable amount being debited from a customer's account without being credited to the selling party. And retrieving this amount is anything but a quick process; one has to inform the site and then wait around 7-10 days before the amount is refunded to their bank accounts. But this situation is steadily improving as the sector is focusing more on cashless transactions and customers are getting more informed about making payments online.

Additional Charges:

How many times has it happened that you've spotted a great deal on a product and when you're one click away from purchasing it you noticed an additional shipping charge. This is commonplace on all e-commerce sites when your order amount isn't high enough to qualify for free shipping. And even when it is, sometimes these shipping charges are added on each individual product (if you're buying multiple products of course) and not the collective order.

Unclear Return and Guarantee Policies:

Since you have no idea of product's quality until you hold it in your hands, returning things bought online is quite common. Unless you're buying from one of the established e-commerce companies, it's important to go through the return policy while making a purchase. But most sites have vague return policies that can leave you with a low-quality product and no way to return it. The same applies for guarantees, as most sites don't clearly mention what the policy is for a product and then refuse to carry out replacements if you receive a damaged product.

Do Not Touch:

Humans are tactile beings and sensory experiences are a fundamental part of their shopping experience. Not being able to physically try out and touch a product is probably one of the biggest cons of online shopping. To make up for this disadvantage, online retailers have to go the extra mile and sell an experience, not just a product.

Suggestion:

Entice your shoppers with compelling product descriptions that highlight the benefits of each feature and appeal to their imagination. The best product descriptions go beyond telling shoppers what the product is and instead explain why it's great for them. Describe how the product feels, how it helps them solve a problem, save time, or how it makes them happier. Complement the text with photos, graphics and videos. Entertain, not just inform.

It's Complicated and Risky:

While shoppers are attracted to complex-looking sites, they are increasingly frustrated by complicated site navigations, overwhelming options and irrelevant details. Studies by Forrester Research estimate that approximately 50 percent of potential sales are lost because your visitors can't find what they are looking for. Your visitors shouldn't have to learn how you want them to navigate your site, it should come naturally. Remove all the clutter that can distract your visitors and allow them to get a good feel for your company and the products you're selling. An effortless and intuitive navigation not only reduces shopper frustration, it's also a great confidence builder. Simply put, make them fall in love with you and your store on first sight.

Lack of Choosing Support:

It's a common perception that having a large assortment of products is key to online domination. However, psychology experts suggest that choosing between a large number of products can be physically exhausting. Offering too many choices without any choosing support is a source of great consumer frustration that you have to be mindful of. Once your shoppers are stressed out, there's every chance that they won't choose anything at all.

Suggestion:

It's crucial to always consider the mind and purchase path of your customer. Many consumers, especially millennial, shop online not knowing what they want exactly, but they know they want it fast. It's your chance to step up as passionate and knowledgeable expert and help them discover products they'll love and offers them ways to easily and intuitively pick the product that's right for THEM.

Receiving Goods Returned by Others:

We've to remember that most top online sellers don't really store the products they're selling. Instead, they've a network of suppliers and retailers who will fulfil your order. And often, these retailers will send you goods that's been returned by others. That's because they're not getting to throw away something and bear losses just because some unhappy customer returns the stuff. Instead, they'll repack it and send it to other buyers. It's very simple to find out whether the seller has indeed sent you something that could've been returned by someone earlier.

Delivery Delays:

And finally, another very common problem with online shopping you can face while shopping online. Delivery delays, this can occur due to several reasons. Generally, bad weather is the biggest culprit since delivery agents can't drive vehicles in heavy rain, snow or stormy conditions because they wish to avoid traffic accidents. A lot of delivery delays also occur because customers fail to provide the accurate address with landmark. Or when you're not at home or office to receive the delivery.

Conclusion:

The study aimed to determine the problems faced by consumers during online purchase. The result showed that most of the respondents have both positive and negative experience while shopping online. There were many problems or issues that consumer's face while using e-commerce platform.

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